

VARIABLE LOADING FATIGUE LIFE OF WOVEN FABRIC CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES UNDER ALTERNATING EQUAL-LIFE WAVEFORMS OF DIFFERENT *R*-RATIOS

M. Kawai and Y. Ishizuka

Department of Engineering Mechanics and Energy, University of Tsukuba
Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305-8573, Japan

Email: mkawai@kz.tsukuba.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.kz.tsukuba.ac.jp>

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ABSTRACT

Effect of repeated alternations in *R*-ratios on fatigue life of a quasi-isotropic woven fabric CFRP laminate has been studied. Fatigue tests are carried out in which two waveforms with different *R*-ratios alternates keeping the number of cycles to failure constant. The fatigue life of the composite under alternating *R*-ratios loading is examined not only for different pairs of stress ratios, but also for different constant values of fatigue life. By comparing the fatigue lives under constant and variable *R*-ratio loading conditions, the effect of repeated alternations in *R*-ratio on fatigue life of the CFRP laminate is elucidated. Finally, prediction of fatigue life of the CFRP laminate subjected to alternating *R*-ratios loading is attempted using a linear cumulative fatigue damage rule in conjunction with the anisomorphic constant fatigue life diagram by which the fatigue lives for the component constant amplitude loading waveforms involved are evaluated. It is demonstrated that the proposed methodology allows predicting a moderately conservative life of the woven composite under any alternating *R*-ratios loading.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber-reinforced plastics (CFRPs) are increasingly applied to structural components in various industrial sectors, not only in the aerospace sector but also in wind energy [1], offshore [2] and high performance vehicle [3] sectors. Fatigue loading that those structural components made of CFRPs undergo during service is not constant amplitude cyclic loading, but variable cyclic loading in general. For reliable application of CFRPs to the key components of structures in the rapidly growing application areas, therefore, it is a prerequisite to establish a method for accurately and efficiently evaluating their fatigue lives under variable loading conditions [4, 5]. This prerequisite involves two main issues to be coped with. One issue is the establishment of an engineering tool by which the fatigue life of CFRPs under constant amplitude loading can be predicted for any stress ratio as well as for any stress level. The other issue is the establishment of an engineering methodology by which the fatigue life of CFRPs can be predicted for any sequence of waveforms of different stress ratios as well as of different stress levels.

To develop our understanding of the effect of load sequence on the variable loading fatigue life of CFRPs and then to establish a method to predict it, we need to study not only the effect of variation in alternating stress amplitude, but also the effect of variation in mean stress on the fatigue of CFRPs. To the best of the present authors' knowledge, however, the effect of variation in mean stress, in other words, the effect of variation in stress ratio, which is independent of the effect of variation in alternating stress amplitude, has not systematically been examined so far, in contrast to comprehensive investigation into the effect of stress ratio on the constant amplitude loading fatigue behavior of CFRPs.

The effect of alternating *R*-ratios loading on fatigue life of CFRPs is considered to contribute to understanding of the latter mentioned above. On a quasi-isotropic woven fabric CFRP laminate, therefore, Kawai and coworkers [6] have performed variable *R*-ratio fatigue tests, in which the stress ratio of fatigue loading alternates between two different values, R_1 and R_2 , under the condition that the

maximum or minimum stress level is kept constant. The alternating R -ratios loading tests were performed for different pairs of stress ratios and for different constant levels of maximum or minimum fatigue stresses, respectively. The effect of alternation of stress ratios on fatigue life of the woven CFRP laminate was quantified in terms of the Miner sum [7] that was calculated using the constant amplitude fatigue life data established in this study. With reference to the Miner sum, applicability of the hypothesis of linear damage accumulation to alternating R -ratios loading was evaluated. From this study, it was found that the fatigue life under the alternating R -ratios loading in which the stress ratio of fatigue loading alternates between two different values keeping the maximum level of fatigue stress at the same constant value is dominantly affected by the fatigue loading at one of the two stress ratios under which the fatigue life becomes shorter. The fatigue lives predicted for alternating R -ratios loading using the Miner rule agreed with the observed fatigue lives with an accuracy of a factor of two. This suggests that the Miner rule is satisfactory in the prediction of fatigue life under the alternation of the two waveforms of different R -ratios but of the same levels of maximum or minimum stresses.

The present study aims to further examine the effect of variation in mean stress on fatigue life of composites through different kinds of alternating R -ratios loading tests and to develop a more detailed understanding of the variable loading fatigue life of composites on the basis of the findings from this study together with those from the previous study [6]. We can consider three kinds of alternations of two waveforms of different stress ratios R_1 and R_2 . The first kind of alternating R -ratios loading is the block loading tested in the previous study [6]. Two waveforms of different values of stress ratio, R_1 and R_2 , alternate under the condition that the maximum or minimum stress levels of the two waveforms are kept constant. In the second kind of alternating R -ratios loading, two waveforms of different values of stress ratio, R_1 and R_2 , alternate under the condition that the fatigue lives for the two waveforms agree with each other. In the third kind of alternating R -ratios loading, two waveforms of different values of stress ratio, R_1 and R_2 , alternate under the condition that the fatigue lives for the two waveforms are not identical. In this study, the second and third kinds of alternating R -ratios loadings are examined. Taking into account all the results from this study and the previous one, we will observe the effect of repeated alternations of mean stress levels on the fatigue of composites in more detail. Moreover, the effect of alternation of stress ratios on the fatigue life of the woven CFRP laminate is quantified in terms of the Miner sum that is calculated using the constant amplitude fatigue life data established in this study. With reference to the Miner sum, applicability of the hypothesis of linear damage accumulation in alternating R -ratios loading is evaluated. On the basis of these observations, we further attempt to integrate the linear damage accumulation rule to predict fatigue failure under variable loading, the rain flow cycle counting method to interpret the complex waveform of loading, and the anisomorphic constant fatigue life diagram approach [8, 9] to predict the fatigue life of a given composite under constant amplitude loading at any stress ratio into an engineering fatigue life analysis methodology. Finally, the variable loading fatigue life prediction methodology developed in this study is tested for the two kinds of alternating R -ratios loadings of the quasi-isotropic woven fabric CFRP laminate.

2 MATERIAL AND TESTING PROCEDURE

2.1 Specimen

The material used in this study was a woven carbon/epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate $[(\pm 45)/(0/90)]_{4S}$ fabricated using a prepreg QFC133-6E01A. The cure temperature of laminates was 350°F (176.7°C). The thickness of laminates was about 3.2 mm. The experimental program in this study includes tension-compression and compression-compression fatigue loadings. For all the tests in this study, therefore, short specimens were used to reduce a risk of buckling due to applied compressive stress. The dimensions of a short specimen are gauge length $L_G = 10$ mm and width $W = 10$ mm. Rectangular-shaped aluminum-alloy tabs were glued on both ends of a specimen with epoxy adhesive in order to protect the gripped portions.

2.2 Test procedure

Static and fatigue tests were conducted under load control at room temperature in a servo hydraulic

(a) Vertical alternation.

(b) Inclined alternation.

Figure 1: Alternating R -ratios loading.

Figure 2: Inclined alternating R -ratios loading.

MTS-810 testing machine. Fatigue load was applied to short specimens in a sinusoidal waveform with a constant frequency of 10Hz. Most specimens were fatigue tested for up to 10^6 cycles, and the fatigue tests that lasted over the cutoff were terminated prior to fracture.

2.2.1 Vertical alternating R -ratios loading

As illustrated in Fig. 1(a), a block of two equal-life waveforms of different stress ratios R_1 and R_2 is repeatedly applied to a specimen until fatigue failure occurs. Note that in the vertical loading tests, $N_1^{(R_1)} = N_2^{(R_2)} = N_f^*$ and $\sigma_{\max}^{(R_1)} \neq \sigma_{\max}^{(R_2)}$. In the vertical (R_1, R_2) alternating R -ratios loading tests, it is assumed that R_1 takes a constant value equal to the critical stress ratio χ ($= \sigma_c / \sigma_T < 0$) for the composite tested, and the critical stress ratio is alternated with a different constant value of stress ratio $R_2 = 0.1, 0.5, 2$ and 10 , respectively. The waveforms of two different stress ratios $R_1 = \chi$ and $R_2 = R$ are combined together, half cycle for each, to form a cycle of new wave, and it is repeated until fatigue failure occurs. The vertical alternating R -ratios loading tests are performed for three different constant values of fatigue life $N_f^* = 10^4, 10^5$ and 10^6 cycles, respectively.

2.2.2 Inclined alternating R -ratios loading

As is illustrated in Fig. 1(b), a block of two unequal-life and unequal-max-stress waveforms of different stress ratios R_1 and R_2 is repeatedly applied to a specimen until fatigue failure occurs. Note that in the inclined loading tests, $N_1^{(R_1)} \neq N_2^{(R_2)}$ and $\sigma_{\max}^{(R_1)} \neq \sigma_{\max}^{(R_2)}$. The inclined alternation of R -ratios may further be separated into two kinds that are associated with the alternation of the lower-left and upper-right points and the alternation of the upper-left and lower-right points, respectively, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The inclined (χ, R) alternating R -ratios loading tests are performed for four

Figure 3: Results of vertical alternating R -ratios loading tests.

different pairs of stress ratios $(R_1, R_2) = (\chi, R) = (\chi, 0.1), (\chi, 0.5), (\chi, 10)$ and $(\chi, 2)$, respectively. Accordingly, we perform six kinds of inclined alternating R -ratios loading tests in total depending on the combination of a pair of two different constant values of life and a pair of two different stress ratios.

The baseline constant R -ratio loading fatigue data that are required to determine the conditions of vertical and inclined alternating R -ratios loading tests have been obtained in the previous study [6] for five different constant values of stress ratio $R = 0.1, 0.5, 10, 2, -1$ and χ , respectively.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Fatigue life under vertical alternating R -ratios loading

Fig. 3 shows the comparison between the fatigue lives under the vertical alternating R -ratios loadings for the four different pairs of stress ratios in the case $N_f^* = 10^4$ cycles. The error bars indicate the range of data bounded by the maximum and minimum values. From Fig. 3, it is seen that the observed fatigue life $N_{f(\text{exp})}^{(R_1, R_2)}$ under vertical alternating R -ratios loading is much shorter than the reference fatigue life $N_{f(\text{pred})}^{(R_1, R_2)}$ predicted using the Miner rule, regardless of the pair of stress ratios. This observation suggests that the use of the Miner rule with the constant amplitude loading fatigue lives for the original waveforms combined in a block gives optimistic prediction of fatigue life under vertical alternating R -ratios loading. The same feature can be seen in the results of the vertical alternating R -ratios loading tests for the different constant values of life $N_f^* = 10^5$ and $N_f^* = 10^6$, respectively.

The detailed observation of the results of the vertical alternating R -ratios loading tests suggests that the deviation of the experimental life from the Miner prediction depends on the pair of stress ratios $(R_1, R_2) = (\chi, R)$ assumed in a block. The experimental results suggest the following inequality relations:

$$N_f^{(\chi, 0.5)} \ll N_f^{(\chi, 0.1)} \ll N_f^* \quad (1)$$

$$N_f^{(\chi, 2)} \ll N_f^{(\chi, 10)} \ll N_f^* \quad (2)$$

$$N_f^{(\chi, 0.1)} \approx N_f^{(\chi, 10)} \ll N_f^* \quad (3)$$

$$N_f^{(\chi, 0.5)} \approx N_f^{(\chi, 2)} \ll N_f^* \quad (4)$$

where N_f^* is the constant value of fatigue life assumed in a vertical alternating R -ratios loading experiment. From these inequality relations, it is seen that a more significant reduction in fatigue life

Figure 4: Log-log plots of observed life versus predicted lives using the Miner rule.

Figure 5: Results of inclined alternating R -ratios loading tests.

occurs under the (χ, R) vertical alternating R -ratios loading when the waveform of the critical stress ratio is alternated with a waveform of a larger level of mean stress, regardless of the sign of mean stress. It is further suggested that the accumulation of fatigue damage until failure depends on the stress ratios that are sequenced in a block of vertical alternating R -ratios loading.

Fig. 4 presents the log-log plots of the fatigue lives observed in the vertical alternating R -ratios loading tests against the fatigue lives predicted using the Miner rule with the constant R -ratio loading lives for the two original waveforms of different stress ratios that are sequenced in a block. The dashed lines in Fig. 4 indicate the range of correlation of a factor of two. From Fig. 4, it is seen that all the fatigue life data obtained from the vertical alternating R -ratios loading fatigue tests are distributed outside the range of a factor of two, and they are distributed in the range of fatigue life from 1/2 to 1/1000 of the fatigue life predicted using the Miner rule. The results in Fig. 4 demonstrates not only that the use of the Miner rule with the fatigue lives for the original waveforms sequenced in a block of vertical alternating R -ratios loading does not allow predicting the vertical alternating R -ratios loading

fatigue life with the accuracy of a factor of 2 that is favorable in engineering fatigue life prediction, but also that it gives significantly optimistic prediction of fatigue life under vertical alternating R -ratios loading.

3.2 Fatigue life under inclined alternating R -ratios loading

Under inclined alternating R -ratios loading, two unequal-life waveforms of different stress ratios, $(R_1, \sigma_{\max}^{(R_1)}, N_{f1}^{(R_1)})$ and $(R_2, \sigma_{\max}^{(R_2)}, N_{f2}^{(R_2)})$, are alternately repeated until fatigue failure occurs. The inclined alternating R -ratios loading may be interpreted as proportional combination of vertical and horizontal alternating R -ratios loadings. Six kinds of inclined alternating R -ratios loading tests, which are designated by A1, A2, B1, B2, C1 and C2, respectively, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 2, were carried out for each of the four different pairs of stress ratios $(R_1, R_2) = (\chi, 0.1), (\chi, 0.5), (\chi, 10)$ and $(\chi, 2)$, respectively.

Fig. 5 shows the comparisons of the experimental fatigue lives under the inclined and vertical alternating R -ratios loadings for the pair of stress ratios $(R_1, R_2) = (\chi, 0.1)$. Note that this figure includes the results of the six kinds of inclined alternating R -ratios loading tests. From Fig. 5, it is seen that the fatigue life data from the inclined alternating R -ratios loading tests are distributed more closely to the band of a factor of two, while they are still outside the band, compared with the fatigue life data obtained from the vertical alternating R -ratios loading tests. This observation suggests that the component of horizontal alternating R -ratios loading involved by the inclined alternating R -ratios loading has an influence of reducing the deviation of the Miner sum at failure from the value of unity.

4 PREDICTION OF FATIGUE LIFE UNDER ALTERNATING R -RATIOS LOADING

4.1 Product waveforms

In the case of vertical alternating R -ratios loading, the two waveforms of different stress ratios that have different maximum (or minimum) stress levels are alternately repeated. Accordingly, the two hysteresis loops associated with the two original waveforms combined in a block shift along the stress axis, and thus one hysteresis loop does not embrace the other. Accordingly, the repeated application of the sequence of these two waveforms has an effect of generating a new hysteresis loop that is larger than either of the hysteresis loops associated with the original waveforms combined to define a block of vertical alternating R -ratios loading. Namely, either the maximum or minimum stress level of the waveform of $R_1 = \chi$ that is accompanied by a larger hysteresis loop is increased by the vertical alternation with the other waveform of a different stress ratio R_2 that is accompanied by a smaller hysteresis loop. Such an expansion of hysteresis loop on average sense should have an accelerating effect on the accumulation of damage during the vertical alternating R -ratios loading. This explains that the vertical alternating R -ratios loading fatigue life is more significantly affected by the variation in stress waveforms not via the original waveforms sequenced in a block but via the product waveforms that are different in stress level and stress ratio from the original waveforms. This is why the Miner sum for the vertical alternating R -ratios loading that was calculated using the fatigue lives for the original waveforms was underestimated, and the significantly optimistic prediction of fatigue life under the vertical R -ratios loading was obtained using the Miner rule.

4.2 Rain flow cycle counting

The product waveforms that are associated with the stress-strain hysteresis loops induced by the original waveforms combined to define vertical alternating R -ratios loading can be identified by means of the rain flow cycle counting method [10]. The fatigue lives for the product waveforms identified by means of the rain flow method are substituted for the fatigue lives for the original waveforms sequenced in the calculation of the Miner sum.

In order to calculate the fatigue life under alternating R -ratios loading by means of the Miner rule, we need the fatigue lives for the produced constant amplitude waveforms of different stress ratios r_1 and r_2 that are different from R_1 and R_2 in general. Accordingly, we are required to predict the fatigue lives for the product waveforms of new stress ratios r_1 and r_2 that are different from the original

Figure 6: Predicted lives using the proposed methodology.

waveforms used to generate the block waveform of testing. The S-N data for those counted new waveforms of different stress ratios are not available in general, and thus we are required to predict them. In the present study, we use the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach [8, 9] to predict the constant amplitude fatigue lives under loadings at r_1 and r_2 , respectively.

The fatigue lives predicted for different vertical alternating R -ratios loadings are compared in Fig. 6 with the observed lives. From Fig. 6, it is seen that the alternating R -ratios loading fatigue lives predicted using the proposed methodology are close to half the observed fatigue lives or even moderately shorter than the observed fatigue lives, regardless of the kind of alternation of waveforms of different stress ratios. The accuracy of prediction of fatigue life using this methodology is thus much better than the accuracy of prediction observed in Fig. 4 that was made by applying the Miner rule to the original waveforms sequenced in the vertical alternating R -ratios loading tests.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of alternation of two waveforms of different stress ratios on the fatigue life of a woven carbon/epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate was examined. For this purpose, two different kinds of alternating R -ratios loading fatigue tests were performed; one is the alternation of equal-life waveforms of different stress ratios, and the other is the alternation of unequal-life waveforms of different stress ratios. Moreover, an engineering fatigue life prediction methodology for predicting fatigue life of composites under complex variable loading was established. The accuracy of prediction of fatigue life using the proposed methodology was evaluated by comparing the predicted and observed lives under different alternating R -ratios loadings. The results obtained from this study can be summarized as follows.

(1) The variable loading fatigue life under alternation of two equal-life waveforms of different stress ratios, which corresponds to vertical alternating R -ratios loading, becomes shorter than the fatigue life predicted using the Miner rule with the constant amplitude fatigue lives for the original waveforms combined to form a block in experiment, regardless of the pair of stress ratios.

(2) The variable loading fatigue life under alternation of two unequal-life waveforms of different stress ratios, which corresponds to inclined alternating R -ratios loading, becomes shorter than the fatigue life predicted using the Miner rule with the constant amplitude fatigue lives for the original waveforms combined in experiment, regardless of the pair of stress ratios, in line with the case for

vertical alternating R -ratios loading.

(3) According to the previous study [6] for fatigue life under horizontal alternating R -ratios loading, the variable loading fatigue life under alternation of two unequal-life waveforms of different stress ratios but of the same value of maximum or minimum stresses can adequately be predicted using the Miner rule with the constant amplitude fatigue lives for the original waveforms combined in the test, regardless of the pair of stress ratios. From the observations in the previous study as well as in this study, it is suggested that the vertical alternation of waveforms of different stress ratios has much larger influence on the accumulation of fatigue damage than the horizontal alternation of waveforms of different stress ratios.

(4) An engineering methodology for predicting fatigue life of composites under variable loading was developed by integrating the Miner rule to determine fatigue failure under variable loading with the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach to predict the constant amplitude loading fatigue lives for any constant amplitude loading and the rain flow method to reduce a complex loading spectrum into a set of simple stress reversals. The alternating R -ratios loading fatigue lives predicted using the proposed methodology are close to half or even moderately shorter than the observed fatigue lives, regardless of the kind of alternation of waveforms of different stress ratios.

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